

Ocean Cities Network (OC-NET)

Summary of activities from June 2021 to May 2023

● The programme at a glance

Ocean Cities is a network of towns committed with a harmonious integration of the urban ocean in the mind, senses and economy of coastal communities. The program aims at enhancing a full connection between citizens and the sea, raising awareness on the essential role that marine ecosystems play in our daily lives and promoting science-based policies and prevention, mitigation and remediation measures against ecosystem degradation and climate change.

WHAT	DESCRIPTION
SCOPE	The Ocean Cities Network (OC-NET) programme involves all basins with special focus in the Mediterranean Sea.
CHALLENGES	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Understand and beat marine pollution. 2 Protect and restore ecosystems and biodiversity. 4 Develop a sustainable and equitable ocean economy. 5 Unlock ocean-based solutions to climate change. 7 Expand the Global Ocean Observing System. 9 Skills, knowledge and technology for all. 10 Change humanity's relationship with the ocean.
AXES	Fostering synergies and collaborative projects in three axes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health: Healthy marine and coastal ecosystems, enhancing individual and collective resilience under the global health approach (challenges 1, 2, 7, 9). ● Culture: Ocean literacy and artistic experiences, incorporating traditional and innovative territorial and ecological knowledge (challenges 2, 5, 9, 10). ● Justice: Science-based transformative policies, supporting a fair transition towards local and global sustainability (challenges 4, 5, 10).
PARTNERS	24 members: 2 research centres (ICM-CSIC and UTM-CSIC) as coordinators. 15 research centres as official partners. 2 city networks that create the connection with city councils. 1 city council directly involved as partner. 7 stakeholder organisations as members of the alliance.
DURATION*	Start Date: 08/06/2021 End Date: 07/06/2025

*OC-net intends to accomplish the 10 years of the Ocean Decade.

This bottom-up collaboration among the coastal society – local administration, private stakeholders, research centres and civil organisations – will set up a participatory and inclusive process aimed at the co-design and co-delivery of science-based initiatives that will change how coastal citizens perceive, interact and evolve with the ocean, and will strengthen the resilience of the coastal settings at social, economic and environmental levels.

With the goal of generating dialogues among scientific, policy and societal actors, OC-NET has identified three axes – health, culture and justice – to establish working groups and develop projects, collaborations and events. All actions settled within these three axes will emerge within the framework of a community-based approach, involving stakeholders, research centres and civil society, building upon local experiences to drive regional and global initiatives

- **Health:** Conceiving actions towards healthy marine and coastal ecosystems, enhancing individual and collective resilience. This axis relates closely to the Ocean Decade Challenges 1, 2, 7 and 9, and the associated outcomes. The health axis aims at generating knowledge for innovative monitoring techniques, advancing in an interdisciplinary approach to understand emerging challenges to the health of the coastal system, and proposing prevention, mitigation and remediation measures that consider social, cultural, economic and environmental issues towards an enhanced coastal resilience.
- **Culture (Society):** Fostering ocean literacy and artistic experiences, incorporating traditional and innovative territorial and ecological knowledge. This axis is closely linked to the Ocean Decade Challenges 2, 5, 9 and 10, and the associated outcomes. The culture or society axis aims at Improving the connection of the cities with their coastal systems. Through the building blocks of blue education and capacity, this axis favours an increased understanding of the interactions between cities and the urban ocean.
- **Justice (Policy):** Promoting evidence-based and science-based transformative policies that support a fair transition towards local and global sustainability. This axis is intimately linked with the Ocean Decade Challenges 4, 5 and 10 and the associated outcomes. The justice or policy axis will promote the exchange of experiences and the creation of alliances with both private and public stakeholders.

Work To Do & vision

Local → Regional → Global

Members of OC-NET fall into two categories: **network partners and alliance associates**. Network partners are actively involved in designing, preparing, and executing actions, while alliance associates primarily support dissemination and communication activities.

Coordinator

[Institut de Ciències del Mar \(ICM-CSIC, ES\)](#)
[Unitat de Tecnologia Marina \(UTM-CSIC, ES\)](#)

Partners

[Centro de Investigación Científica y de Educación Superior de Ensenada \(CICESE, MX\)](#)
[Centro de Investigaciones del Mar y de la Atmosfera Instituto Franco Argentino para el estudio del Clima y sus Impactos \(CIMA, AR\)](#)
[Oceans & Atmosphere University of Queensland \(CSIRO, AU\)](#)
[Universidad de Concepción \(CL\)](#)
[Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas y Costeras \(INVEMAR, CO\)](#)
[Universidad de las Palmas de Gran Canaria \(ULPGC, ES\)](#)
[Marine and Environmental Science Centre University of Coimbra \(MARE,PT\)](#)
[University of Cape Town \(MARIS, ZA\)](#)
[National Institute of Oceanography Council of Scientific & Industrial Research \(CSIR, INDIA\)](#)
[Università degli studi di Genova \(UNIGE, IT\)](#)
[Università Politecnica delle Marche \(UNIVPM, IT\)](#)
[Tokyo University of Marine Science and Technology \(TUMSAT, JP\)](#)
[Universidad de Antioquia \(CO\)](#)

Barcelona Local Council
[Medcities](#)
 C40

Alliance

[Bau Design College \(BAU, ES\)](#)
[ECSA European Citizen Science Association](#)
[INGENIO CSIC-UPV \(ES\)](#)
[Las Furas dels Baus \(ES\)](#)
[Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn \(SNZ, IT\)](#)
[SEA-EU Thee European University of the Sea](#)
[Universidad de Antioquia \(CO\)](#)

Within the program, cities are represented by the Barcelona local council, as well as two city networks: MedCities and C40. MedCities is an organisation that includes 63 cities in the Mediterranean basin, coordinated by a secretariat based in Spain, with a focus on sustainability. The C40 coalition is a global alliance of 95 cities dedicated to seeking and implementing solutions against climate change, with the coordination currently held by Barcelona.

● The 2021-2023 programme activities

The list of actions presented next represent the principal actions carried out in the frame of OC-NET for its two first years of life. Internal meetings within the coordination and among partners are not included in this list.

WHAT	DESCRIPTION
Coordination	<p>Assemblies with all OC-NET members (once per semester).</p> <p>Launch up of the website (October, 2021) www.ocean-cities.org</p> <p>Press communication for social media and preparation of presentations and posters at events.</p>
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordination of a session in the conference <i>An Ocean of Values. The 5th Community Workshop</i> of the IOC-UNESCO Ocean Best Practices System (September 20-24, 2021 - Online). ● Coordination of two Ocean Decade laboratories, promoted by Germany, after the Ocean Decade kick-off on the objectives of the decade, <i>Laboratory A Predicted Ocean Minka Project</i>, (September 16, 2021; <i>Towards a clean and sustainable Mediterranean Sea</i> (November 18, 2021). ● Coordination of a session in the II International Forum on Marine Litter and Circular Economy. <i>Hands on circular solutions for healthy oceans</i> (May 16-20, 2022. Seville, Spain). ● Coordination <i>Side event on Science Toward Sustainable Ocean UNOC22</i> (June 27-July 1, 2022. Lisbon, Portugal). ● Ocean Cities month in Barcelona (Spain) (October 2022): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Organisation of 2 round tables on Gender perspective in coastal management (October 1, 2022). ○ Blue School debate with teachers (October 6, 2022). ○ Round table on The sea and Sustainability (October 7, 2022). ○ One workshop on Plankton as the Driving Force of Life (October 8, 2022). ● OC-NET joined the EU mission Charter (October, 2022). ● OC-NET participated in three of the EU Mission Ocean & Waters launch event: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse, Ireland (January, 2023). ○ EU Mission Forum, Brussels (February, 2023). ○ Mediterranean Lighthouse, Italy (May, 2023). ● Ocean Cities month in Barcelona (Spain) and Antioquia (Colombia) (October 2023): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Activities in both cities during the entire month

WHAT	DESCRIPTION
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in the Plastic Buster CAP Event: Fostering knowledge transfer to tackle marine litter in the Med (April, 2022. Online meeting). • Organization of a round table about Ocean Cities: Dialogues between citizens and the ocean, <i>15th Science Fair</i> (May 28, 2022. Barcelona, Spain). • Oral presentation at <i>Moby Litter III Seminar</i> (July 14, 2022. Ancona, Italy). • Conference Press at the CSIC headquarters for the presentation of the book "The ocean we want: inclusive and transformative ocean science, Pelegrí JL, Gili JM Martín de Albéniz MV (eds) (June 8, 2022. Madrid, Spain). • Oral presentation at the kick-off meeting of the EuroMarine TransOcean working group (<i>Outlook on Transoceanic, Transversal and Transformative International Ocean Programs</i>) (January 19, 2023).
Knowledge products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statement of the Spanish Delegation at UNOC22 – <i>Interactive dialogue 1: Addressing Marine Pollution</i> (June 27, 2022. Lisbon, Portugal). • Publication of a book entitled <i>The ocean we want: inclusive and transformative ocean science</i>, Pelegrí JL, Gili JM Martín de Albéniz MV (eds), Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC Barcelona, (June, 2022). <i>The book had both physical and electronic formats, the latter available in several open sources, including the UN Ocean Decade catalogue: https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000384371</i> • Setup of October as the Ocean Cities month. In the frame of this month, all OC-NET partners will prepare actions (events, seminars, round table, workshop, exhibitions and cultural events) in their own cities. Actions will revolve around one or more of the programme axes. The 2022 edition was a pilot initiative held in Barcelona in collaboration with the city council, the 2023 edition will be held simultaneously in several different cities.
Bottom-Up Synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The University of Antioquia (Colombia) has started two coastal erosion projects: PIMECLA, a natural laboratory for mitigating coastal erosion in Antioquia, and Red CoCo, a Citizen Science initiative. These projects are carried out with the support of other two OC-NET partners: ICM and the Universidad de Las Palmas Gran Canaria. • With the support of ICM, the Center for Sea and Atmosphere Research (Argentina) has engaged in impact mitigation and adaptation actions to potential changes in the coastal zone, in collaboration with the Ministry of Science and the Environmental Directorate of the city of Buenos Aires. • With the support of ICM and the University of Gambia, a network of primary and secondary schools is being created, with the central objective of generating knowledge to co-design future solutions to environmental challenges.

WHAT	DESCRIPTION
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICM-CSIC, the University of Concepción (Chile) and the Redplus Foundation (Chile) are joining forces to address coastal erosion and governance issues in the BioBio region of Chile. • Together with partner institutions from Senegal, Argentina, Colombia and Mexico, ICM-CSIC submitted a proposal to strengthen international collaboration networks. • Ocean Cities, through ICM-CSIC, has supported the multinational company ISDIN to create the BlueWave Ocean Alliance, aimed at conservation and regeneration of coastal and marine ecosystems.

● The 2021-2023 parallel activities

The following list corresponds to actions carried out in the frame of the Ocean Decade where OC-NET, with ICM-CSIC as coordinator, has been involved.

Ocean Cities managed the community of practice (CoP) on Coastal Resilience until February, 2023 (CoP8 – Coastal Ecosystem and Community Resilience).

The main actions developed in the framework of this coordination are the following:

- Coordination of the platform, members and forum.
- Coordination of the CoP8 first meeting. *Community of Practice 8 and coordination of the Meet and Greet* (November 22, 2022).
- Set up of the CoP definition and its objectives by means of a participatory process.
 - i. Definition. The CoP8 is a community of practice under the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, an open space to debate and exchange best practices about coastal areas around the world.
 - ii. Objectives. The following objectives were established, which are currently used by the new version of the CoP that is directly coordinated by DCC:
 - Human interaction and connectivity.
 - Coastal area fragmentation, in terms of socio-economic and environmental perspectives as well as in terms of knowledge and best practices.
 - Engagement of society.
- Set up of the keywords for CoP8
 - I. Engagement and Community: engagement to develop fit-for purpose science, community engagement, proximity, support, synergy, and stakeholder engagement.
 - II. Culture, Awareness and Territory: Cultural heritage, perception and interaction with coastal ocean, archaeology, dissemination, history.

- III. Ocean, Ecosystems and Resilience: Ecosystem health and functioning, coastal ocean, climate change, estuaries, key habitats, wetland conservation link nature and resilience, land-sea connectivity, resilience, knowledge of coastal ocean, human and coastal health, clean ocean.
- IV. Socio Economy and Governance: Sustainable blue growth, usage of new science-based information products for the coasts, socioeconomics, circular and sustainable, marine spatial planning, social and build environment, best practices in coastal area, capacity building.

OC-NET is part of the programme scientific committee of the Collaborative Center on Coastal Resilience led by the University of Bologna. This Decade Collaborative Centre for Coastal Resilience (DCC-CR), based in the University of Bologna, provides support to the Decade Coordination Unit by catalysing and coordinating Decade Actions related to coastal resilience.

As part of the Ocean Decade, the DCC-CR will contribute primarily to Challenge 6: Increase community resilience to ocean hazards. It will do so by supporting endorsed Decade Actions, catalysing new Decade Actions, promoting stakeholder engagement, supporting communication and awareness rising & outreach, facilitating mobilisation of resources, and monitoring & evaluation. Some initial examples are:

- Oral presentation at the kick-off of the DCC-CR, (January 18, 2023. Bologna, Italy).
- Providing support to the DCC-CR in the transition from the CoP-8, including four meetings.
- Participation in the DCC-CR executive committee through an OC-NET partner (the Polytechnic University of Marche, Ancona, Italy).